

Información 3D

Camera systems

Establish a mapping from 3D to 2D

How to calibrate a camera

Estimate camera parameters such pose or focal length

Single view metrology

Estimate 3D properties of the world from a single image

Extraer informacion 3D de una unica imagen es un “ill-posed” problem

Necesitamos varias cámaras para reconstruir la información 3D

Example: Stereo Vision

Multiple view geometry

Structure from motion

Structure from motion

Courtesy of Oxford **Visual Geometry Group**

3D urban modeling

[Bing maps](#), Google Streetview

Source: S. Seitz

3D urban modeling: Microsoft Photosynth

<http://labs.live.com/photosynth/>

Source: S. Seitz

3D Models

Scanning Michelangelo's *"The David"*

- [The Digital Michelangelo Project](http://graphics.stanford.edu/projects/mich/)
 - <http://graphics.stanford.edu/projects/mich/>
- 2 BILLION polygons, accuracy to .29mm

Fotometria: como se crea la imagen

Photometry Overview

Source emits photons

And then some reach an eye/camera and are measured.

Photons travel in a straight line

They hit an object. Some are absorbed, some bounce off in a new direction.

Light Transport

Source emits photons

Illumination

Photons travel in a straight line

And then some reach an eye/camera and are measured.

They hit an object. Some are absorbed, some bounce off in a new direction.

Light Transport

Source emits photons

And then some reach an eye/camera and are measured.

Photons travel in a straight line

Surface Reflection

They hit an object. Some are absorbed, some bounce off in a new direction.

Light Transport

Source emits photons

And then some reach
an eye/camera and
are measured.

Sensor Response

They hit an object. Some are
absorbed, some bounce off
in a new direction.

Perception: Color Constancy

Humans are very good at recognizing the same material colors under different illumination. Not clear how this is achieved in the general case.

Image processing

Filtrado y suavizacion

Operadores lineales
Convolucion
Suavizado

Image processing

An **image processing** operation converts an existing image f to a new image g

Can transform either the domain or range of f

Image processing

Range transformation: $g(x, y) = t(f(x, y))$

(What is an example?)

Noise filtering

Image Processing

Domain transformation: $g(x, y) = f(t_x(x, y), t_y(x, y))$

(What is an example?)

Translation

Rotation

Algunos procesos típicos

Feature extraction

Derivadas de la imagen
Contornos
Operadores de gradiente
Detectores de esquinas

Se buscan descriptores mas informativos que los pixeles

3D modeling of landmarks

Luz y color

Radiance / Reflection
Illumination / Shading
Chromaticity
Color Constancy

Aplicacion: Deteccion de piel

Web applications

Photometria

Modelos de proyeccion de camara

Parametros intrinsecos (lente) y extrinsecos (pose)

Calibracion de la camara

Aplicacion: Eyevision

Eyevision : SuperBowl XXXV

January 28, 2001

Super Bowl XXXV

January 28, 2001
Courtesy of CBS Sports

Sports (<http://www.sportvision.com>)

Virtual first down line
([explanation](http://www.howstuffworks.com) on www.howstuffworks.com)

Real-time strike zone box

Ball tracking

Virtual Ads!

Plane to Plane Mappings

Rigid, Similarity, Affine, & Projective Mappings
Homography Estimation
Image Warping

Mosaicing and Stabilization

Camera Rotation Homography
Mosaicing
Video Stabilization

Panoramic Photography

Stereo Vision

Stereo Camera Setups

Stereo Disparity / Parallax

Epipolar Geometry

Correspondence Matching

Triangulation / Depth Recovery

Camera Motion

Motion Field vs Optic Flow
Flow Estimation
Egomotion Estimation
Structure from Motion

Application: Autonomous Driving

Have your vehicle chauffeur you around.

Stanley, winner 2005 Darpa Grand Challenge

Video Change Detection

Video Sequences
Background Modeling
Change Detection

Application: Video Surveillance

Automatic detection, classification and tracking of moving people and vehicles

Object locations are determined with respect to a 3D campus model

A single operator can monitor results from many sensors spread over a large area

Video Tracking

Appearance-Based Tracking
Sample Tracking Algorithms
(e.g. Mean-Shift, Lucas-Kanade)

Object Recognition

Library of models

Model matches (using Lowe's SIFT keys)

Approaches: PCA; Sift Keys; boosted cascade of detectors

Application: Face/Eye Detection

Henry Schneiderman

Finding users to interact with.
Red-eye removal from photos.
Drowsy-driver detection.

Face detection

BBC NEWS

UK version International version About the versions | L

Last Updated: Monday, 6 February 2006, 14:29 GMT

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Face-hunting cameras boost Nikon

Japanese camera maker Nikon has tripled its profits on the back of strong sales of digital cameras that automatically focus on human faces.

Face recognition cameras like the Coolpix L1 are popular

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Northern Ireland
Scotland
Wales
Business
Market Data
Your Money
E-Commerce
Economy
Companies
Politics
Health
Education

Face detection

Sample image: Subject as seen on the COOLPIX 5900 camera's color LCD and when using Nikon's Face-priority AF function.

Smile detection

The Smile Shutter flow

Imagine a camera smart enough to catch every smile! In Smile Shutter Mode, your Cyber-shot® camera can automatically trip the shutter at just the right instant to catch the perfect expression.

[Sony Cyber-shot® T70 Digital Still Camera](#)

Source: S. Seitz

Image search engines

Visual search and landmarks recognition

Google Goggles

Visual search and landmarks recognition

Augmented reality

Special effects: shape and motion capture

Source: S. Seitz

Motion sensing and gesture recognition

Automotive safety

manufacturer products consumer products

Our Vision. Your Safety.

rear looking camera forward looking camera side looking camera

› **EyeQ** Vision on a Chip

› **Vision Applications**
Road, Vehicle, Pedestrian Protection and more

› **AWS** Advance Warning System

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- › Mobileye Advanced Technologies Power Volvo Cars World First Collision Warning With Auto Brake System
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- › Mobileye at Equip Auto, Paris, France
- › Mobileye at SEMA, Las Vegas, NV

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[Mobileye](#): Vision systems in high-end BMW, GM, Volvo models

Computer vision and Applications

Factory inspection

Assistive technologies

Surveillance

Autonomous driving,
robot navigation

Vision for robotics,
space exploration

Security

Biometrics

How the Afghan Girl was Identified by Her Iris Patterns

Source: S. Seitz

Optical character recognition (OCR)

Technology to convert scanned docs to text

- If you have a scanner, it probably came with OCR software

Digit recognition, AT&T labs

License plate readers

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Automatic_number_plate_recognition

Source: S. Seitz

Medical imaging

Image guided surgery

[Grimson et al., MIT](#)

3D imaging
MRI

Mercados

